

From Soapbox to Poetic Mentor Through the Revolution of the Word: The Education of Kenneth Rexroth¹

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The autodidact Kenneth Rexroth ended his formal education when he was expelled from high school in Chicago for insubordination, including a claim that he had nothing to learn from the classes he was taking at the school. He also made an announcement concerning Leninist doctrine, and refused to attend military training (Hamalian, 1991, p. 12). But this major figure of the San Francisco Poetry Renaissance who later, for a short time, provided mentorship for Allen Ginsberg, Gary Snyder, and other Beat writers, did not stop his education when he found himself on the streets of Chicago. Home-schooled through his early teens, he became an orphan and entered the public school system as a ward of relatives, and after his expulsion continued his education by attending lectures at the University of Chicago, going to the Field Museum and the Art Institute, and frequenting the Newberry Library, where he read voraciously, as he recounts in his *Autobiographical Novel*. Much of his education also came from the bohemian clubs, “at-homes,” and open-air forums where soapboxing professors mingled with bums (Brundage, 2004, p. 89). These unusual sources formed the backdrop to an alternative education that nonetheless brought the poet to a deeply nuanced understanding of the nature of knowledge. His interactive experience of soapbox culture influenced his thinking and his mature poetics, affecting his stance as a poet, mentor, anarchist, activist, and intellectual. It underlies the pattern Rexroth identifies in his longer works as a “philosophical reverie ... in which voices come and go,” each presenting a view of life that is “contradicted by the spokesman for the other member of the polarity” (Rexroth, 1968, p. vii) before moving into transcendence. Mixing mythologies, philosophies, political positions, the sacred and the profane, the lofty and lowly, Rexroth’s works, and especially his long poems, offer a mélange of rhetorical incursions that recalls the mix of hobo and professor he found at Bughouse Square, and reflect the intense, interactive pursuit of wisdom and insight that in many ways explains why the Beats were attracted to him.

It took Rexroth several years to settle on the poetics of declamation and concentrate on the personal voice that underlies his long poems of the 1940s and 1950s. This feature of his works binds him to the Beats and impacted postmodern American poetry generally. While his life in 1920s hoboemian Chicago strongly affected his intellectual bent, activist lifestyle, and poetics, Rexroth deliberately undertook a lengthy exploration of the stylistic and aesthetic experiments of the literary avant-garde before he settled on the mature mode one could call a “soapbox” poetics. Along with his work in poetry, his extensive reading, interest in the artistic experiments of his contemporaries, and endeavors as a painter, stage designer, and actor fueled this exploratory period. An attraction to what he calls “The Revolution of the Word” (Rexroth, 1969b, p. xiv) led him to

¹ Some of the material in this article is a revision of earlier work published in *2006-2007 Proceedings of the Midwest Philosophy of Education Society Annual Conferences* and *Journal of Beat Studies*.

educate himself in the styles, theories, and practices of major literary movements of his day, involving him in exploration and/or criticism of Modernist Symbolism, Dadaism, Surrealism, Objectivism, and Literary Cubism. These phases mark the poetry he wrote before he settled into the mode of political and philosophical declamation, didactic presentation, and direct address that marks his mature style—the dominant style during his association with the Beats and the one in which he served, if sometimes only in his perception of himself, as a mentor.

The Soapbox

Rexroth threw himself into hobohemia after moving to Chicago in 1919. He quickly discovered what Slim Brundage called America's intellectual center (Brundage, 2004, p. 89). The Chicago Renaissance had seen writers and editors like Carl Sandburg, Sherwood Anderson, Harriet Monroe, and others establish themselves. Chicago was a crossroads for intellectual and literary stars because of its universities and importance as a center in the American railroad system. Prohibition and women's suffrage were sparking an era of feminist rebellion impacted by the waves of illegal alcohol that made Chicago famous as a capital of bootlegging.¹ With the First World War over, soldiers returned to jobs that had been filled by Blacks and others in the wartime economy. Unions fought to protect jobs in the tradition of worker radicalization evidenced by the Haymarket bombing, the Pullman strikes, and the founding of the IWW in Chicago in 1905, the year of Rexroth's birth. In 1919, the year Rexroth moved to Chicago, deadly race riots rocked several major American cities. In Chicago order was restored only with the arrival of 6,000 state militia men (Reynolds, 1986, p. 166). Such tensions influenced the tremendous boost in popularity of both the Ku Klux Klan and the back-to-Africa movement of the Garveyites.²

As a teenage orphan during this period, Rexroth witnessed the left's response to these events, especially in the communist, anarchist, and Wobbly circles he frequented in Chicago and later while travelling throughout the country and abroad. Opposition to the oppressive capitalist system had been bolstered by the seeming breakdown of western society in in the First World War, coupled with the revolution in Russia. War fever before the United States entered the conflict encouraged persecution of those who opposed intervention, including "pacifists, Socialists, [and] members of radical labor unions such as the IWW" (Weinstein & Rubel, 2002, p. 545). In 1917

¹ The connection between prohibition and feminism might seem far-fetched, but becomes clearer if one considers the diversity—often generational—of women's positions in conjunction with the rise of flapper culture. The suffragettes supported the Volstead Act along with the right to vote. As Caryn E. Neumann points out, "The gap between the beginning of national Prohibition and the creation [in 1929] of the WONPR [Women's Organization for National Prohibition Reform, an anti-Prohibition women's group] can be attributed to the hope evident among many women that the law would in fact result in a moral cleansing of the United States." However, Neumann continues, "By the time Prohibition began to be perceived as the cause of much disgraceful conduct among the citizenry—including a rise in intemperance—significant numbers of women protested the amendment" (Neumann, 1997, p. 34). Put another way, the 1920s saw a rise in "women's hedonism" and the development of a female culture of "consumption: consumption of mass industrial products, consumption of mass culture and mass media, consumption of urban nightlife, consumption of sexuality" (Reinsch, 2012)—and, of course, consumption of alcohol, helping fuel the crime wave behind the fortunes of Capone and others.

² For general comments on the racist atmosphere of Wilson's presidency, see Loewen (2005), particularly pp. 466-473. For Klan activity in Chicago, see Jackson (1992), pp. 93-126. According to Jackson, in the early 20s "Chicago ranked high as a national center of Klankraft" (p. 126), though membership declined rapidly in 1924. Garveyism prospered in Chicago during this period, boasting several thousand members and hosting several UNIA divisions in Chicago, mainly on the south side. See "Garveyism" (2005).

Congress created an agency in charge of propaganda (COPI, the Committee on Public Information) to solidify the war effort. While generating support for the war, this move also engendered hatred and fear of opponents to America's involvement (Weinstein & Rubel, 2002, p. 545). This led, for example, to renaming sauerkraut "liberty cabbage"¹ and a ten-year sentence (later commuted) for Eugene V. Debs for defending the Bolshevik Revolution, pacifists, and the Wobblies in a speech. After the war, xenophobic fears shifted from Germany to Russia, leading to the Red Scare of 1919-1920 (Weinstein & Rubel, 2002, p. 546). The leader of the fight, Attorney General A. Mitchell Palmer, often failed to distinguish between Bolsheviks and Socialists (Weinstein & Rubel, 2002, p. 546), confused protest with revolution, and saw Blacks, Jews, and feminists as threats to democracy (Weinstein & Rubel, 2002, p. 547). Radical left reaction exploded.

The political and cultural focus of such events energized the soapbox forums that Rexroth describes as "a most important working class—or at least migratory working class—educational institution" (Rexroth, 1991, p. 139). In this era, before the development of national or even local broadcast media, interpretation of the news often fell to soapbox orators who would explain what lay behind the page, and sometimes spent hours doing research in preparation (Rosemont, 2006, p. 154). Information dissemination was not yet consolidated in corporate structures, so the soapbox circuit lent itself to individualized and often radical expression. Radio only started being celebrated as the great new democratic medium in 1925, when newspapers that commended or criticized soapbox culture began to call soapboxing 'passé' (Trasciatti, 2013, p. 62). Of the Chicago soapbox presenters Rexroth recalls Whitey Miller, who could lecture on a census report or the *World Almanac*, and John Loughman, the liaison between Chicago's mayor and hobohemian society (Beck, 2000, p. 90), who would "get up on the box with the daily paper or a weekly news in his hand and comment on the contents," interpreting events in a way that made him "the spokesman and ... philosopher of this whole group of completely disaffiliated revolutionaries" (Rexroth, 1991, p. 141). Other speakers covered topics from the African Blood Brotherhood to Kierkegaard and Nietzsche (a three-week lecture series given by Triphammer Johnson) to oral sex as a form of contraception, an answer to "the problems of Malthus and Marx" (Rexroth, 1991, p. 140). All topics were viable. As Rexroth describes it,

every night until midnight could be heard passionate exponents of every variety of human lunacy. There were Anarchist-Single Taxers, British Israelites, self-anointed archbishops of the American Catholic Church, Druids, Anthroposophists, mad geologists who had proven the world was flat.... Besides, struggling for a hearing was the whole body of orthodox heterodoxy—Socialists, communists (still with a small 'c'), IWWs, De Leonites, anarchists, Single Taxers ... Catholic Guild Socialists, Schopenhauerians, Nietzscheans—of whom there were quite a few—Stirnerites, and what later were to be called Fascists. (Rexroth, 1991, pp. 105-106)

Because of its extraordinary mix of topics, soapboxing allowed individualized diffusion of knowledge (and of pseudo-knowledge) and interpretation. Its closest modern cognate might be social media and blogging, or perhaps far-right talk radio, but it existed without possibilities for international dissemination, and with a built-in control of immediate, unmitigated, in-your-face heckling or even physical attack. The soapbox scene in Chicago consisted of a "regular city circuit"

¹ Cf. the naming of French fries as "freedom fries" after France decided not to join the "coalition of the willing" during the 2003 Iraq invasion.

through which Rexroth found it “possible to make quite a decent living” (Rexroth, 1991, p. 139). Main locations included corners on Madison near the Hobo College, the Haymarket, Navy Pier, the Bug Club in Washington Park on the South Side and, in the Near North, Washington Square in front of the Newberry Library, still known as Bughouse Square. As part of the circuit, Rexroth quickly learned how to profit from soapboxing; as he puts it, “if I made all these points over a weekend I could always pick up a minimum of fifty dollars—a lot of money in those days for two days work for an adolescent boy” (Rexroth, 1991, p. 139). He focused on “bringing poetry to the masses,” developing skills in poetry performance that foreshadowed the emphasis on spoken-word poetry and oral performance that saw a re-emergence with the Beats. But he also describes a stint as a professional heckler. When hucksters started hawking the “Abrams electronic diagnosis machine,” Rexroth got hired to “[go] around to public meetings addressed by the Abrams-machine apostles and [ask] embarrassing questions ... demonstrating to the assembled innocents that a fourteen-year-old boy ... could expose the fraud” (Rexroth, 1991, p. 120). His usefulness lasted as long as his anonymity.

Rexroth’s role here illustrates one trademark of the soapbox forums—their interactive quality. Any topic broached was open for debate or derision. This was part of the attraction. At Bughouse Square, lectures on the most outrageous topics were accompanied “as a bonus” by fervent heckling that often was as entertaining as the lectures themselves (Rosemont, 2004, p. 11). Crowds could number in the thousands, and there could be “two or three dozen ‘ozone orators’” (Rosemont, 2004, p. 11) speaking simultaneously, as well as clusters of argument called “beehives” (Brundage 90). The attraction is reflected in the popularity of the Dil Pickle club, created by Wobbly Jack Jones, Irish Labor leader Jim Larkin, and others to serve as an “indoor Bughouse Square” (Rosemont, 2004, p. 12). Artists, writers, aldermen, critics, professionals, tourists, high school students, university debate teams, and professors from Northwestern, DePaul, and other Midwestern universities came, not to mention speakers from Paris, Bombay, and elsewhere. Similarly, from 1910 to 1930 Bughouse Square was described as the most notorious center for outdoor free speech in the nation (Rosemont, 2004, p. 11). It fostered working class education (a high Wobbly priority) and incarnated Chicago-style anarchism, becoming central to what Rexroth called the “Anarchist Twenties” to distinguish it from the “Red Thirties.”

And what did Rexroth learn from all this? One of his clearest expressions of what he gained appears in his account of “the Judge,” who “created singlehanded an all-encompassing system of dissent” with “the intelligence of an Aristotle or an Aquinas” that “disagreed all along the line with all organized thought” (Rexroth, 1991, p. 107). The Judge’s lectures combined economics with cosmology, and mixed Greek, Hindu, Zoroastrian, and Finnish mythology. They depicted the “galactic universe” as “an immense organism” whose “heavenly bodies were its cellular parts” (Rexroth, 1991, p. 107). Comets were involved in insemination of planet-ova, and Noah’s flood led to “a diffusion of culture over the earth from ... the Aryan Commune of Mesopotamia, where the survivors of the Ark, a whole city of men and animals, had settled after the Flood” (Rexroth, 1991, p. 108). The vision, consistency, and mass of evidence impressed the adolescent boy, but, Rexroth notes, “like all other totally organized paranoias, it was impossible for the nonparanoiac to accept.” Rexroth concludes,

The Judge taught me that all knowledge has its unreal system. St. Thomas Aquinas has all the answers but he ignores most of the questions. So, to a lesser degree, does Lyell

or Einstein.... The Judge taught me to sit lightly, not just to human opinions but to philosophy and science, and to appreciate it all as a great work of art—man’s construct over and against the ultimately unfathomable universe. (Rexroth, 1991, pp. 109-110)

For Rexroth, insights from the Judge and others whom he characterizes as the “lunatic fringe” led him to think that the “orthodox view of the universe,” though not necessarily wrong, existed as it did “only because millions of men [consented] to seeing the universe in that way” (Rexroth, 1991, p. 119). This intuitive recognition of the untruth, inaccuracy, or incompleteness of human interpretation possibly underlies Rexroth’s claimed intention in his long poems of creating perspectives from competing philosophies that move towards “dialectic resolution” in “unqualified, transcendent experience” (Rexroth, 1968, p. [vii]).

The Revolution of the Word

If, as he claims, Rexroth’s long poems follow a pattern of contradiction followed by transcendent resolution, his poetics of declamation and clear radical expression definitively emerged only after he underwent a period of intense self-education in the avant-garde movements of his day. This exploration involved him in the literary equivalents of the radical changes that were occurring in the plastic arts and music at the time. Collectively he calls this trend in literature “The Revolution of the Word,” and at the time he claimed that many writers felt that these experiments “would liberate a new life meaning for man and sweep away dead shells from which meaning had been exhausted or had turned malignant” (Rexroth, 1969b, p. xiv). In other words, before he reached a poetics of direct political and philosophical exposition and a stance as poetic mentor, Rexroth progressively schooled himself in Imagism and High Modernism, explored Dadaism and reacted to Surrealism, and found camaraderie with the Objectivists while ultimately identifying with Literary Cubism. All these movements reflect literary expressions of tendencies found in the other arts of the period, such as what was happening in painting (cf. Cubism, such as in the works of Picasso) and in music, where serialism and other explorations of tonality or dissonance were occurring, not to mention the emergence of spontaneity and improvisation epitomized by jazz.

Rexroth’s exploration of these literary movements and his experimentation with their strategies and styles illustrate his intention of finding artistic forms that would truly serve as “the instrument of a fundamental revolution of human sensibility” (Rexroth, 1969b, p. xiv). In order to explicate the dialectic structure that he claims underlies his long poems, he uses *The Homestead Called Damascus*, a poem he claims he completed before leaving Chicago at age 20 but that was only published in the 1950s. The poem drifts through diverse settings and cityscapes, pulling in an array of philosophical, literary, and mythological motifs, allusions, and characters ranging from Bishop Berkeley to Mordred to Origen to Tammuz. It uses a style reminiscent of the early poems of T. S. Eliot by incorporating allusion and reference to mythic and literary themes. Its mix also calls to mind the depiction Rexroth gives of The Judge, who blended economics and cosmology with Greek, Hindu, Zoroastrian, and Finnish mythology.

Mostly presented in the third person, *The Homestead Called Damascus* centers on two brothers, Sebastian and Thomas Damascan, with a third, ironic “narrative” voice interjecting, and also with various representations of the feminine that Rexroth traces back to his girlfriend of the time (see Rexroth, 1991, pp. 256-257). (The reference to Damascus in the title and the main characters’

names of course evoke the world of polarization between materialism and spirituality represented by the New Testament figure of Saul/Paul, who experiences transcendence in his vision of Christ on the road to Damascus, an event that turns him from a tax-collector into an evangelist.) Rexroth claims that the poem evokes “the interior and exterior adventures of two poles of a personality” (Rexroth, 1968, p. [vii]), and Sebastian and Thomas do appear to represent the martyr-artist (Sebastian) and the doubting or skeptical philosopher (Doubting Thomas and/or Thomas Aquinas, with a side-glance at Tammuz/Adonis, a sacrificial vegetation Deity). Morgan Gibson contends that the brothers seem ill defined as separate characters (see Gibson, 1972, p. 40), but Rexroth claims that the two “[argue] with each other right to the last page, [while] the third figure—the anonymous observer—is ... making wry comments” (Rexroth, 1968, p. [vii]). The poem starts with their squabbling, traces their individual odysseys, and ends with them posing somewhat disparate though interacting stances regarding human individuality and agency:

Thomas says, “There is no self subsistent
Microcosm.” He thinks a while of
Chuang Tzu ... and
Says, “There is no self subsistent
Macrocosm either....”

Sebastian said, “I am the master of the
Pattern of my life, freedom
Is the knowledge of necessity....” (Rexroth, 2003, pp. 55-56)

Thomas’s recognition of interdependency is in fact reflected by Sebastian’s contrary assertion of self-mastery (perhaps a feature of martyrdom), colored by an immediate linking of “freedom” to “knowledge of necessity,” i.e., knowing what is needed or essential. If freedom depends on necessity, that is, it involves recognizing what must or has to be. The two positions thus turn toward each other while initially representing disparate stances. This philosophic sleight perhaps launches the moment of “transcendence” into a broader, non-rational confrontation with the world when Thomas, at the end of the poem, hears the sound of a train passing in the night “like a diamond necklace falling / Through the long somber valley ... / ... / Like some bright micro organism” (Rexroth, 2003, p. 64). The journeys that take the two through physical and mythical realms conclude in nature, in the west, and in the reality of a train whistle blowing, linking the transcendent with the real as Rexroth does when he claims that “[t]he holy is in the heap of dust—it is the heap of dust” (Rexroth, 1968, p. [ix]).

Despite the poem’s interesting peregrinations, the stylistic avenue explored in *The Homestead Called Damascus* did not satisfy Rexroth—or Harriet Monroe, who Rexroth claims declared the poem “a lot of talky-talk” (qtd. In Rexroth, 1991, p. 257) and encouraged him to write about machinery. *Homestead* demonstrates an aesthetics Morgan Gibson characterizes as Symbolist and reflects Rexroth’s exposure to high Modernism, most notably as reflected in the early works of T. S. Eliot and in Conrad Aiken’s “mood of elegiac reverie” (Lipton, 1957, p. 38). It also reflects the poetry of English Decadence, which Rexroth knew well from his soapboxing days. Rexroth explains his exposure to the Decadents and his recognition of their poetic efficacy in his *Autobiographical Novel*:

All during the period of Proletarian Art I found the discussion of proletarian poetry rather unreal, because I had actually tried poetry on the proletariat and my experience didn't match the theories at all. [On the soapbox circuit] I used to recite Patrick Magill, Service's *Songs of a Wage Slave*, Belloc's poem to his little son, Vachel Lindsay's socialist poems, Lola Ridge, James Oppenheim, Arturo Giovanitti, and all the other old chestnuts of revolt.... This was all right with the stiffes, but what they liked best was the world-weary poetry of the English Decadence—the *Rubáiyát*, Housman, Ernest Dowson, and best of all, Swinburne's "The Garden of Proserpine." This always made a perfect number to go out with and added substantially to the collection. I've often thought, roaring it out into the windy night under a sputtering arc lamp, that its last verses perfectly reflected the hopes and ambitions of the average hard-rock miner, lumberjack, or harvest hand. (Rexroth, 1991, p. 142)

The elegiac reverie of *The Homestead Called Damascus*, along with the emotional emphasis of his early poems that he connects with the styles of F. S. Flint, Richard Aldington, and other poets associated with the Imagist movement, certainly show a sense of world-weariness, not to mention a self-conscious ambiguity that reminds one of Eliot's Prufrock, complete with "vague, inconclusive, meandering metaphysical and theological conversations" (Gibson, 1986, p. 40). Rexroth describes the poetry he was writing at the time as spurred by "adolescent sentiments" (Rexroth, 1991, p. 256). The overwhelming experience of reading *The Waste Land* when it first came out left him "half-conscious" and influenced his poetry in a way he calls "entirely for the bad" (Rexroth, 1991, p. 257). The poem's "dissociative style," which Rexroth says Eliot "borrowed from Apollinaire," at the time seemed "revolutionary, and the picture of decay ... was so overpowering that it seemed to be a revolutionary rather than a reactionary indictment" (Rexroth, 1991, p. 257). Rexroth in fact states that he assumed that Eliot's published notes concerning the "moral collapse of civilization in Eastern Europe" contained a "typographical error for Western Europe" (Rexroth, 1991, p. 257).

The impetus to discover "a style that would be especially my own, free of literature and with some relationship to what I was able to do in painting" (Rexroth, 1991, p. 256), thus lay behind *Homestead*. Rexroth says of the poem, "a lot of Frazer and Jane Harrison and Jessie Weston crept into it and didn't do it any good. Eliot's tone of weary, disillusioned withdrawal crept in as well" (Rexroth, 1991, p. 257). The influence of Eliot becomes immediately apparent in lines such as "Botticelli ladies, slim / And hyperthyroid, grace the walls" (Rexroth, 2003, p. 29; cf. Eliot's lines from "The Love Song of J. Alfred Prufrock," "In the room the women come and go, / Talking of Michelangelo"), and in the passage where "Sebastian dreamed and saw ... / ... / ... [his girlfriend's] favorite poems turned down / On the sewing table, and shadows / Curled like tabby cats around the pots..." (Rexroth, 2003, p. 30). But the poem does have effective moments of intense, Byronic romanticism:

Somewhere quests a strange simplicity.
And oh, my music, when she walks
In beauty, through smoking traffic
Between the twilight skyscrapers
The verve undulance of the lonely
Heart. Are you my Narcissus pool?

Brilliant rockets of the sun dappled
Waterfall? Young and beautiful with
Old eyes and quick feet. Philosopher—
No hunk of this matter will receive
Any impression of the pure Idea.
(Rexroth, 2003, p. 46-47)

Another feature one recognizes is the oblique Cubist impact, matching Rexroth's painterly ambitions (see Appendix), and evinced in literary terms in the beginning of the poem, with its imagistic description of angels "robed / In tubular, neuter folds of pink and blue" (Rexroth, 2003, p. 25). Further instances occur in the description of the world as "composed of a pair of / Broken pillars, a round sun in a / Rigid sky, a sea, and in the great / Distance, a red line of cliffs" (Rexroth, 2003, p. 43), and in Sebastian's sudden discovery of "the footprint / Of a Picasso nude on the dull / Red sand beneath the grey heat of skies" (Rexroth, 2003, p. 29). Rexroth also toys at the start of the poem with a passage from James Joyce's *Ulysses* by mentioning the "ineluctable modality of the invisible"; chapter three of *Ulysses* starts with Stephen Dedalus on Sandymount Beach thinking of the "Ineluctable modality of the visible" and the "ineluctable modality of the audible" while considering the "Signatures of all things" (Joyce, 1986, p. 75), which became the title of one of Rexroth's books of poetry. The chief factor influencing his style in the poem, though, seems to be Eliot, and after *Homestead* Rexroth immersed himself in other styles in an effort to educate himself away from this feature. He in fact claims that he and other poets were only "able ... to write ourselves out of Eliot's idiom ... due to the fact that we had more wholesome examples in French verse" (Rexroth, 1991, p. 258).

This effort to move away from the Modernist style of Eliot may best be represented in Rexroth's brief exploration of the world of Dada, a more multi-mediated form of artistic expression, and also his criticism of Surrealism, a movement more aesthetically oriented than Dadaist nihilism. These exemplars of French experimentation impacted his work, but ultimately, he rejected them. His attraction to the anti-rationalist and anti-aesthetic qualities of Dadaism seems short-lived. He formed a "deliberately abortive Dadaist movement" with Lawrence Lipton and Sam Putnam. Calling themselves "Escalator," they gave poetry readings and lectures that Rexroth describes as involving competing readings from Kant and the telephone book while accomplices in the audience fired blanks and set off alarm clocks (Rexroth, 1991, p. 304). Escalator engaged in other activities, including a staged parade at a department store involving "rented evening clothes, Halloween false faces, plug hats, and ... open black umbrellas" (Rexroth, 1991, p. 305). The "Escalator Manifesto," circulated at the time but apparently published for the first time by Franklin Rosemont in the 2000s, presented "Escalator [as] the backfire of the hindbrain / against the conflagration of reason," "the cordon sanitaire against gangrene and good sense," "the ass on the altar, the pope's jock-strap," and so on (Rosemont, 2006, p. 160). The problem, Rexroth claimed, was that Escalator became successful "just as we began to realize that we were being silly and dated. So after one last all-night party ... we buried the Escalator movement for good" (Rexroth, 1991, p. 305).

What probably influenced Rexroth's rejection of Dada was his recognition of its ultimately bourgeois emphasis. He recalls an Escalator performance in a largely black club after which "a beautiful young girl ... got up and gave a long speech about how we were a perfect example of the

bankruptcy of Western civilization” and how “the future belonged to a world view that was just then aborning—on the South Side, for instance” (Rexroth, 1991, p. 305). Such criticism of course would not sit well with his radical proclivities.

Rexroth’s quick foregoing of Dada is coupled with his attack on Surrealism, which he associated with the Dadaist movement. Like Dadaism, Surrealism seeks to forego or displace rationality. But while Dada assumes an essentially nihilistic posture in its anti-rationalistic and anti-aesthetic emphasis, Surrealism routes its critique through explorations of the world expressed in the subconscious and manifested in dream. André Breton, a main figure in the Surrealist movement, describes Surrealism as a “resolution of . . . two states, seemingly so contradictory, of dream and reality, in a kind of absolute reality, a surreality” (Breton, 2010). In its purist form Surrealist writing involved “psychic automatism by means of which one [expresses] the actual functioning of thought” without “any control exercised by reason” and “free of any aesthetic or moral concern” (Breton, 2010). This emphasis on exploration of the unconscious and the dream-state was not to Rexroth’s taste. Rexroth characterizes Surrealism as a “quest [for] hallucination,” and asserts that his poems are “the opposite of Surrealism” (Rexroth, no date b).

Rexroth makes a poetic attack on Dadaism and Surrealism in his poem “Fundamental Disagreement with Two Contemporaries” (Rexroth, 2003, pp. 83-89), a poem that, owing to Rexroth’s own strategies when he wrote it, might present interpretive problems comparable to or even more complex than those found in works by the Dadaist Tristan Tzara and the Surrealist André Breton, the “contemporaries” to whom the poem is dedicated. In fact Rexroth claims that the poem parodies Surrealist style (Rexroth, no date b). “Fundamental Disagreement” stands as Rexroth’s statement against Tzara and Breton since these two artists attack rationality with nihilism or, in Surrealism’s case, the unconscious, offering “the omnipotence of the dream” and the “permanent destruction of all other psychic mechanisms” (Breton, qtd. in Argüelles, 1975, p. 211). Using language linked to scientific, philosophical, geographical, and other fields of discourse, the poem moves from seeming incoherence to the presentation of a “CONCEPTUAL PERSPECTIVE ENGINE” (Rexroth, 2003, p. 83), a de-animated entity that seemingly generates or maintains concepts and perspectives, or perspectives on concepts. From the “CONCEPTUAL PERSPECTIVE ENGINE” we

modulatepersistendurereverserevolvereciprocateoscillateperpetuate

until we “ARRIVE” at a quasi-mathematical and overtly philosophical statement concerning extant, abstracted objects—“there exists an *a* / there exists an *i*” (Rexroth, 2003, p. 84). These objects become significant through triangulation via the existence of a third entity: “one other entity *b* / ... / ...vests the prospect with originative continuity / the dominative pervasive accommodation of aspect / ... thus assimilating contingency / or the contingent as hiatus in the populous / meaning fused with recipient” (Rexroth, 2003, p. 84). The granting of continuity and aspect thus seems to remove contingency from meaning. “[E]ntity *b*,” which is “valid / efficient / potent,” allows “meaning” to become “fused with [its] recipient” through *b*’s “originative continuity / the dominative pervasive accommodation of aspect.” We might think of entity *b* in relation to the controlling “CONCEPTUAL PERSPECTIVE” generated by the “ENGINE.” Multiple views, or “aspects,” are central in the Cubist or Objectivist work, the angle from which Rexroth attacks Dadaism and Surrealism, as long as these views are dominated by the aspect

engendered in the form of *b* “without projective meaning” (Rexroth, 2003, p. 84). Continuity may theoretically be what provides or permits meaning, confounding or confirming interpretations tacked on by the “recipient” through “assimilating contingency” or making “the contingent” a “hiatus in the populous / meaning” of the work. One could say that meaning results from continued association of subject and object, while contingency temporarily interferes with meaning.

If we divide this section of the poem in two, seeing the portion up to and including “ARRIVE” as a satire of surrealism, the “CONCEPTUAL PERSPECTIVE ENGINE” potentially also becomes both “recipient” and generator of meaning through its filtering down in the first part into “the personal pronoun.” In this case *b* functions as the recipient that creates meaning by assimilating the contingent through “the pressure of significance” (Rexroth, 2003, p. 84). This “pressure” exists largely because “importance endures with intervals” (Rexroth, 2003, p. 84); time fuses possibilities of interpretation, fostering the assigning of significance. Thus in fact any aspect of a work that exists in time potentially achieves significance simply via duration and the application of significance to it by the “CONCEPTUAL PERSPECTIVE ENGINE,” which is an aspect of the recipient of meaning. It is as if two interacting entities generate a third entity formed by the relation of the first two. Meaning then comes to resemble possibility itself, as Rexroth suggests in a poem from his mature period, “The Dragon and the Unicorn”:

Although the possibilities
Of each instant are infinite
They are the possibilities
Of only that instant, that point
Of triangulation in which
The person places himself
In relation to others. (Rexroth, 2003, p. 359)

This highly philosophical analysis of the origin of meaning marks one of the distinctions between Rexroth’s works and the intentions of the Dadaists, who attack the “bourgeois emphasis” on meaning as a category of existence, and the Surrealists, who elevate expression of the unconscious above specific rationalistic meaning. By locating a ground for significance in something as simple as the extension of existence as it is realized in each moment (recall that “[t]he holy is in the heap of dust—it is the heap of dust” [Rexroth, 1968, p. (ix)]), Rexroth attempts to deny the nihilism or irrationality he associated with Dadaism and Surrealism. He does this in “Fundamental Disagreement” through invoking a theme that becomes increasingly important in his works, the establishment of meaning through relation.

Rexroth may have given his final poetic dig at the “traditions” of Anglo-American Modernism and of French Dada/Surrealism in his poem “Into the Shandy Westernness,” which first appeared in the inaugural issue of *Pagany* and may have been read before publication by William Carlos Williams, to whom it is dedicated. Williams had agreed to perform editorial functions for the journal and mentions reading a “mass of script” that he “marked as well as I have been able to mark it” (Williams, 1969a, p. 38). On his own behalf Williams contributed an appreciation of Gertrude Stein that draws heavily on Laurence Sterne, possibly reflecting some of Rexroth’s own focus in “Into the Shandy Westernness” (with its pun on Sterne’s *Tristram Shandy*) and his stern, or *Sterne*, assessment of Anglo-American and French literary currents:

Whenever I think of England I see Wyndham Lewis standing in a high freezing wind on the plain where Mordred and Arthur fought, dressed only in his BVDs painfully extracting thorns from his chapped buttocks. It grows dark rapidly.

When I think of France I see Marcel Duchamp on Michigan boulevard in a raccoon coat and a number of young americans praying before a roller-coaster from which middle aged Frenchmen strapped to bicycles leap into tubs of coca-cola.

Ta-tum ta-tee I love you

There'll ne'er be none above you

Even when you do

Fa down and go boom

BOOM boom BOOM boom boom (Rexroth, 1969a, p. 52)¹

The cold, caustic view of Anglo-American Modernism, represented here by Wyndham Lewis, brings with it the mythological (Mordred and Arthur) and painfully displays Modernism's propensity to confessionalist exposure. Think of Eliot's Prufrock; Rexroth, in his poem "Codicil," describes Eliot's poetry, like that of Valéry and Pope, as not just "Personal" but "intense / ... / Intimate and revealing, / Embarrassing if you will, / As the indiscretions of / The psychoanalyst's couch" (Rexroth, 2003, p. 600). French Dada and Surrealism, on the other hand, represented here by Marcel Duchamp, express themselves in imagery drawn from American pop-culture, involving absurdities interestingly set in Chicago if we take "Michigan boulevard" for Chicago's famous Michigan Avenue. The lyric mocking popular music at the end only reinforces this populist banal aspect of such forms of artistic expression, as well as perhaps reflecting the introduction of popular song that characterizes parts of Eliot's "Wasteland."

Rexroth's interest in the presentational immediacy of the multi-faceted perception of meaning explored in "Fundamental Disagreement" suggest why he was drawn to Cubism and Objectivism. His chief aesthetic inclination throughout this period of exploration and discovery might in fact most closely be described as Literary Cubist. As we have suggested above, these inclinations mark his reaction against the nihilism and hallucination of Dada and Surrealism. However, limiting his work to a "school" or seeing it as embodying the ideas presented in a "manifesto" invariably does his poems an injustice. Dorothe (later Dorothy) Van Ghent describes the intention behind Literary Cubism as being to present as fully as possible the reality of the subject by offering multiple elements of it simultaneously, thereby achieving "presentational immediacy" as opposed to limitation to "causal efficacy" (Van Ghent, 1935, pp. 31-37). She states that the "presentational immediacy" in Rexroth's Cubist writings serves "to build up particularities of existence in the simplest possible manner. Any poetic *form* that obtains is the form of the existents themselves" (Van Ghent, 1935, p. 116). We see this in the long listing sections of Rexroth's poem "A Prolegomenon to a Theodicy":

The white the large

The slow movement

The type of dream

¹ The *Pagany* version of "Into the Shandy Westernness" differs slightly from the version in Rexroth's *Collected Poems* (Rexroth, 2003, pp. 92-94). For example, the five lines of mock song lyric have been cut in the *Collected Poems* version. Capitalization or lack thereof in the passage is Rexroth's own.

The terror

The stumble stone

The winter the snow that was there (Rexroth, 2003, p. 123)

The movement of the poem involves fragmentary descriptions of impressions or perceptions meant to evoke sensations stimulated by the presence of the object. For Van Ghent this sort of presentation allows objects to be “eternalized (philosophically, at least) by their very apparition” (Van Ghent, 1935, p. 116).

Objectivism might best be understood via William Carlos Williams’ dictum “no ideas but in things,” though it must be coupled with the recognition that “‘self-contained’ interpretations [are] objective (contextual) not ‘subjective’ in nature,” and that “the appearance of the art form [is] an object” in and of itself (Louis Zukofsky, qtd. in von Hallberg, Autumn 1973-Winter 1974, p. 87). In philosophical terms, the Objectivist movement could perhaps be described as inspired by Alfred North Whitehead, who claims that “the things experienced and the cognizant subject enter into the common world on equal terms” (Whitehead, qtd. in von Hallberg, Autumn 1973-Winter 1974, p. 85). The main literary figure associated with Literary Objectivism, Louis Zukovsky, would probably have denied this, though, as he felt that philosophy had no place in poetry. But Whitehead’s equation of “the things experienced and the cognizant subject” links Objectivism to Literary Cubism, which attempts to achieve a merging of multiple views into a singular experience and “present the poetic vision of a cosmic, simultaneous form in a period of reductive processes” (Nitzberg, 1988, p. 42). Via strategies that imitate “the effects of technological progress: syncopated phrasing and the heterogeneous juxtaposition of planes to suggest simultaneity” (Nitzberg, 1988, p. 40), the aim, attempted through the juxtaposing of aspects of an object, is to capture the “simultaneity, dynamism, [and] space-time structures of the Fourth Dimension” with its “entangled sensory associations” (Nitzberg, 1988, p. 41).

Whitehead contends that the objective process creates an egalitarian relation between subject and object without which nothing would exist (see Ross, 1986, p. 106). This condition resembles the triangulation described in “Fundamental Disagreement,” where the relation of subject and object creates a third entity expressed as and through the relationship formed by the interacting of two entities. Von Hallberg comments that Objectivism thus seems “to be not so much literary reactions against a century of subjectivism and symbolism in poetry” as an attempt “to construct aesthetic theories that would answer to the challenge posed by 20th century scientific thought and technological achievement” (von Hallberg, Autumn 1973-Winter 1974, p. 88). We can see these tendencies expressed in Rexroth’s poetry of the inter-war period, and so can sense the ways they problematize interpretation of his work. Rexroth posits the poem as a construct and approaches it with a simultaneous mixture of presentation, impersonality, and objectification. He argues that Zukovsky’s call for Objectivism was mostly “a statement of the classic swing of the pendulum away from romanticism,” and that “Zukovsky was almost totally under the influence of Ezra Pound’s *Cantos*” (Rexroth, 1991, p. 447). Regarding his own poetics, he admits that “For several years [he] was completely dominated by Whitehead’s philosophy,” and that Whitehead gave him “the modern foundations for a philosophy of organic process and of immanent, rather than

transcendent, deity” (Rexroth, 1991, p. 391).¹ What appears ultimately to have caused him to reject Objectivism is his argument with Louis Zukovsky over the role philosophy should play in the poem. For Rexroth, as we might sense from the argumentative structure of “Fundamental Agreement” or from the title of his ‘Objectivist’ poem “Prolegomenon to a Theodicy,” philosophy was bound to and potentially ever-present in poetry. For Zukovsky, philosophy and poetry were antithetical to each other, a view of poetry that Rexroth associated with naïve romanticism (Rexroth, 2006).

William Carlos Williams’ appreciative essay on Gertrude Stein, who is often thought of as the originator of Literary Cubism, can in some ways be seen as taking an Objectivist stance, in that it describes “Stein’s theme [as] writing. But in such a way as to be writing envisioned as the first concern of the moment, dragging behind it a dead weight of logical burdens.... [Stein] has placed writing on a plane where it may deal unhampered with its own affairs, unburdened with scientific and philosophic lumber” (Williams, 1969b, p. 56). Williams’ interest in Stein’s ability to devolve from the rationalizing burdens of language reflects his Objectivist credo “No ideas but in things,” and so points to a position toward writing that tries to avoid the external referents that predetermine meaning through established association. Rexroth’s poems also engage in the breaking up and rebuilding of verbal elements in a way that recalls how Cubist painting fractures visual elements, and it also “reflect[s] his studies in primitive song and modern linguistics” (Knabb, 1990). His poems of this period thus sometimes display instances of linguistic fragmentation and metalinguistic commentary that show the extent to which he approached the poem as an object to be manipulated from all fronts simultaneously. “To the Shandy Westernness,” for instance, plays on mathematical analysis (“Let event particle e. Point track m-n”), chess (“P to K3, Kn x B”), hymns, popular song, vernacular, and so on. In his poem “In the Memory of Andrée Rexroth,” metalinguistic punning lets us analyze the poem as an object at the same time that it provides commentary on the tragic facts of pain, loss, death, and memory that are its topic:

On the reality of loss and tense
And the participation of loss and tense
Where loss is an imagined real
And tense may break in case
i.e.: as aorist breaks in instrumentals
dative garment and ablative
informant. Distinguish that the problem is not
of being and the dilemma is
not scalar and it is not differences
but distinctions that matter.... (Rexroth, 2003, p. 63)

The plays on the words “tense” and “case” involve us both in the pain of loss and the linguistic construction of the experiences of passing and memory. The “aorist,” which expresses a simplified presentation of the past with no suggestion of continuation or repetition (Macdonald, 1972, p. 56), “breaks in instrumentals,” perhaps musical, but also suggesting the means or “instrument” (Macdonald, 1972, p. 680) that allows recollection. Here this breaking involves perhaps an

¹ For insight into differences between Rexroth’s Zukovsky’s aesthetics, see Rexroth’s letter “To Louis Zukovsky” (Rexroth, 2006, pp. 17-24) and Riley’s article (Riley, 2014, pp. 1-10) on Rexroth’s ‘Objectivist’ poem “Prolegomenon to a Theodicy,” which Zukovsky at one point edited to get it to align it with Objectivist principles.

“indirect object” (“dative garment,” which could be a memory evoked by an article of clothing) and the “ablative / informant,” pointing to the ablative case “which in Indo-Germanic languages originally expressed *direction from*, or *time when*” (Macdonald, 1972, p. 3). The levels of abstraction here and in other poems depend upon recognition of the extent to which language is structuring perceptions of reality. It is language after all that permits or makes cognizant recognition of the past, or memory, as well as all poetry. As in the case of “Fundamental Disagreement,” the defamiliarization of the subject through its treatment estranges the reader from the context, thus potentially fulfilling the “instrumental” purpose of generating “a fundamental revolution of human sensibility.”

Rexroth’s objectivism thus refuses or counteracts Williams’ intention of unburdening the languages of science and philosophy. In fact, it directly incorporates them, as well as the metalanguage of linguistics, into the constructed aesthetic object of the poem. This tendency indicates why Rexroth’s focus on the presentational immediacy of Literary Cubism would lead him to reject Objectivism. For Rexroth, the philosophical aspect introduces perspectives that can be just as important to the experiencing of the object as perception of the object itself. It becomes the grounding of all that depends in Williams’ famous poem about the red wheelbarrow, with its introductory hint that dependence hinges on the object, but fails to ground that dependence in the psychic and linguistic construction of the observer or seer for whom the dependence is instrumental. Williams’ dictum “no ideas but in things” may in fact forego the opposing condition that things exist equally in the perceptions, linguistic constructs, and ideas we bring to them. This is a main point in the revolution of the word Rexroth explored so intently in his slow elucidation of the poetic schools that dominated the avant-gardes of his time.

Poet, Philosopher, Mentor

All these trends represent the artistic possibilities and problematics Rexroth turned away from when he developed what could be called a poetics of declamation or of the soapbox. His intense immersion into and schooling in the practices, manifestos, and underlying theories regarding Modernism, Dada, Surrealism, Literary Cubism and Objectivism ultimately seems to have convinced him that the revolution to be brought about by the word was best served by clarity of meaning and straight-forward rhetorical transparency. This shift in direction represents a turn from indirect statement of radical intent via form towards an equally radical direct statement of intent via content. It also helps us link Rexroth’s poetics with the poetics of the Beats and the writers of the San Francisco renaissance and underscores his affinities with these writers.

In the 1940s Rexroth began hosting literary “at homes,” perhaps reminiscent of those educative meetings he had known in Chicago, and soon he was at the center of the famous San Francisco poetry renaissance. In 1953 young Gary Snyder first attended. For Snyder, “Kenneth [was] a catalytic figure” who gave “a lot of reinforcement” at a time when “the Partisan Review was talking about the failure of intellectual America” (Snyder & McKenzie, 1987, pp. 4-6). In 1954 Allen Ginsberg showed up, equipped with a letter of introduction from William Carlos Williams (Miles, 1989, p. 171). Ginsberg and Snyder first met at one of these at homes, and soon, according to Lawrence Ferlinghetti and Nancy J. Peters, Rexroth was “a father figure for the Beats.... Many of his attitudes and interests were theirs, especially ‘disengagement’ from materialist-militarist society together with a turning to the Far East’s literature and ‘Buddha consciousness’”

(Ferlinghetti & Peters, 1980, pp. 175-76). Rexroth appears in particular to have helped Ginsberg develop his poetic technique; he encouraged Ginsberg to move away from formalistic qualities in his verse, leading Ginsberg to later describe “Howl” as “within Rexroth’s genre” (qtd. in Gifford & Lee, 1978, p. 222). The poem does bear striking similarities to Rexroth’s elegy to Dylan Thomas “Thou Shalt Not Kill” (Woodcock, 1983, p. 80). The famous Gallery Six reading in 1955 introduced the Beats to the world, as did Rexroth’s introductory letter to the “San Francisco Scene” volume of *Evergreen Review* (1957). But by the time the *Evergreen Review* volume came out a rift between Rexroth and the Beats had formed, largely because of a drunken argument involving Kerouac, Ginsberg, Snyder, and others during which Ginsberg boasted of being a better poet than Rexroth.

Throughout 40s and 50s Rexroth developed a declamatory poetic style that involved direct statements of political and philosophic positions. I see this poetic approach as reminiscent of the soapbox rhetoric he had known during his adolescence in Chicago. Morgan Gibson comments that “because even some of his friends in the avant-garde did not comprehend his cubist poems, [Rexroth] decided to reach a wider community of readers by writing very much as he spoke, in normal syntax” (Gibson, 1978, p. 43). In the long poems this often takes the form of moving from descriptions of nature or narrations of travels to meditations or declamations that sometimes interject straightforward philosophical or political positions, often tagged with “As the philosopher says.” These passages often move toward the didactic. Take, for example, “The Phoenix and the Tortoise,” which Rexroth calls “a poem of general philosophy based ultimately on the Mahayana Buddhist sutra ‘The Kegon Kyo’ ... strung on quotations from ... an anthology of the greatest Japanese poems” (Rexroth, 1991, p. 497). This description presumably depicts an underlying structure (though Gibson says that the poem’s “personalism, sacramentalism, and sense of responsibility ... clearly come from Christianity” [Gibson, 1978, p. 70]). But the poem also depends on a rejection of collectivity via a movement toward a world-vision in which the individual—perhaps an individual like that “ragged hobo in a gaslit room off West Madison Street” whom Rexroth depicts as being able to construct his own relatively coherent explanation of the world—becomes the organic center of a perspective that calls into doubt all organized systems, replacing order with faith in the final recognition that “the only Absolute is the Community of Love with which Time ends” (Rexroth, 1968, p. [viii]). The long poems of this period mix description or narration with “soapboxing” expressions of political and philosophical positions. We see this occurring in “The Dragon and the Unicorn” in passages on persons and objects, with the argument that “The person is real / Only in community” (Rexroth, 2003, p.457). In “The Phoenix and the Tortoise” similar positions are articulated through passages where the person is pitted against the state:

The State is the organization
Of the evil instincts of mankind.
History is the penalty
We pay for original sin.
In the conflict of appetite
And desire, the person finally
Loses; either the technology
Of the choice of a lesser evil
Overwhelms him; or a universe

Where the stars in their courses move
To ends that justify their means
Dissolves him in its elements. (Rexroth, 2003, p. 250-251)

The philosophical and political posturing present positions that could almost be taken for lessons before moving to the moment of vision that finishes each poem. In this way his long poems reflect the lively circulation of ideas that characterized the culture of the soapbox, the Dil Pickle Club, and the “at homes” that Rexroth knew as an adolescent in Chicago. What Rexroth calls “transcendental empiricism” represents an interpretation he associates with “a statement in philosophical terms of the I. W. W. Preamble” (Rexroth, 1968, p., [viii]), one he sees as counteracting the basic tendency of modern capitalistic society to commodify all existence. As Rexroth argues, “It is easy to overcome alienation—the net of the cash nexus can simply be stepped out of, but only by the self actualizing man” (“Rexroth, 1968, p., [ix]). If this sounds fantastical, if it calls for a heckling, it is nevertheless a vision, perhaps a Romantic one, and it relies ultimately upon faith, not reason—or perhaps on faith supported by a reasonable questioning of the tenets of reason, by looking at the questions that underlie reason. It points to the insight that “all knowledge has its unreal system.”

How can we characterize this phase of Rexroth’s poetic evolution, which in many ways aligns him with the message and the poetics of the Beats and marks the impact he may have had on them? For one, we can say that the poet is engaged in straightforward political or philosophic speech. Because of this the content and presentation are sometimes didactic in nature. The speech in these passages is declaimed in a way that might reflect the spontaneity of direct presentation, determined by its orality as discourse in a way that for instance recalls much of Beat writing. Rexroth’s poems move through simple rhetorical statements to moments of questioning that might even mimic response to a confrontation. Though Rexroth claims it represents “competing philosophies” that “come and go,” it shifts via its dialectic toward a conclusive moment that he characterizes as transcendent vision. A passage from “The Phoenix and the Tortoise” reveals this pattern:

War is the health of the State? Indeed!
War is the State. All personal
Anti-institutional values
Must be burnt out of each generation.

“As the Philosopher says,”
Man is a social animal;
That is, top dog of a slave state.
All those lucid, noble minds admired
Sparta, and well they might....

.

They say that history, defining
Responsibility in terms
Of the objective continuum,

Limits, and at the same time creates,
Its participants. They further say
That rational existence is
Essentially harmonic selection.
Discarding “is,” the five terms
Are equated; the argument closed.
Cogito and Ergo and Sum play
Leapfrog—fact—process—process—fact —
Between my sleeping body and
The galaxy what Homeric
Heroes struggle for my arms? (Rexroth, 2003, pp. 251-252)

We note the thematic link to the Beat message—and to that of the Wobblies, the anarchists, and others—which Gary Snyder described as “beautifully reinforcing” since it offered “anarchism as a credible and viable position” (Snyder & McKenzie, 1987, pp. 4-6). Rexroth’s identifying of “the State” with “War” directly implicates all organized political systems with the destruction of individuality and personhood. The underlying three- to four-beat dactylic rhythm adds emphasis, generally stressing the first syllable. This rhythmic control may explain why Woodcock felt it ironic that Rexroth’s poetry was less well-known than the “inferior” poetry of the Beats (Woodcock, 1983, p. 81). This rhythmic strategy gives emphatic tone to direct attack, mimicking a haranguing speech style one might associate with the soapbox. (Michael McClure, who started attending Rexroth’s literary salons with Philip Lamantia in 1955, described the rhetorical flourishes in Rexroth’s speech as “swashbuckling” [McClure, 2003, p. 13].) The statement “War is the health of the state,” posed here as a rhetorical question, is emphasized immediately by the amplifying interjection of “Indeed!” The passage then presents societies as deliberately and necessarily attempting to control “personal / Anti-institutional values” and “personality.” Philosophical perspectives on the warrior state of Sparta, introduced by “As the Philosopher says,” depict society as crushing individuality, and war as (ironically) existing to “take care of persons” in the sense both of protecting them and getting rid of them. The reference to the philosopher also helps deflect the message so as to suggest the introduction of another, albeit not competing, perspective. Strong stress combined with alliteration brings emphasis to the metaphoric placement of man as “Top dog in a slave state.” Moving away from straight political and philosophical speech, the poem passes into a more meditative passage touching on the limitations and possibilities of history, then reflects back on the archetypal “Homeric / Heroes” who struggle for the narrator’s “arms,” both his weaponry and his embrace.

In this excerpt, the soapbox haranguer merges with the meditative, the questioning, and the descriptive to advance through a philosophical reverie presented as “dramatic dialog” (Rexroth, 1968, p. [vii]), though with only one voice—the speaking “I”—addressing a non-voiced “you” who is both the reader and the other component in the “two poles of a personality” identified with Sebastian and Thomas in Rexroth’s first long poem. If “the political stance of the poems never changes” (Rexroth, 1968, p. [viii]), this is because it restates “in philosophical terms ... the I. W. W. Preamble” and “the cash nexus passage in *The Communist Manifesto*”—rhetorical positions Rexroth was early made aware of through his reading but equally through his exposure to radical soapbox culture.

Conclusion

By the 1950s the soapbox was gone, replaced by radio, television, and, in our age, social media with all its miracles and dangers. These media institutions formulated social organization through centralized communicative systems that only now, in the cyberspace of the blogosphere and social media, is being challenged through the “circulation vs. dissemination” model of media spreadability. If soapboxing was an educative tool that was allowed because it permitted release in order to control, contain, or express revolutionary idealism as a movement of ideology toward a utopic free dissemination of ideas, we can say the same thing for Rexroth’s poetry. In fact Rexroth worked for over twenty years as a presenter and organizer of radio station KPFA, which he described as “a noncommercial educational FM station, owned and operated by Pacifica Foundation, a democratically run, more or less cooperative, board of local leaders of every variety, united largely by their sense of community responsibility” (Rexroth, no date a). He was able to use this platform to offer educational, albeit nontraditional, “sustained literary and cultural discussions over the airwaves” (Houglum, 2007, p. 56) for many years.

Bill Nichols describes “Revolution [as] the explosive eruption of dialectical processes of contestation that occur all the time in ... far more unobtrusive form” (Nichols, 1986, p. 100) and suggests (quoting Lentricchia) that “The rhetoric of aesthetic power is born in the linkage of form with ideology in its two psychosocial domains ... as overt ‘culture,’ however ‘upside down’ ... and as a sort of unconscious that Althusser called a ‘lived relation to the world’” (Lentricchia, qtd in Nichols, 1986, p. 101). The soapbox can be understood as a form of this “unobtrusive” contestation, and its assimilation before its basic disappearance in the 1930s (with noted exceptions) removed this form of expression from general culture, into a realm now largely dominated recently in America by such extreme right voices as Rush Limbaugh and Alex Jones. In the soapbox, as a performative and educational medium, an aesthetic of spontaneous and not-so-spontaneous interaction between speaker and audience linked form and culture, both overtly and as “lived relation.” That this world is increasingly subverted by electronic and mediated forms of communication serves as a model or form of control perhaps even beyond the ken of the controllers under whose watch these forms have evolved. Rexroth hinted at such centralized controlling devices when in “The Dragon and the Unicorn” he asserted that whenever a modern couple “wish / To satisfy their passions, / They go to a movie” (Rexroth, 2003, p. 430). Against this is posited the straightforward, in-your-face communication of the soapbox, in some ways continued, contained, depoliticized, and trivialized in the “in your face” television spectacles of the Jerry Springer sort and more recently in the cybersphere. Rexroth attempts in his poetry to retain the voice of the culture of his youth as his defense against the wearing of time and the increasing “alienating, destructive pressures of modern secular thought and history, in which each person is reduced to an atomic individual in perpetual conflict with other individuals” (Gibson, 1978, p. 71).

A last note, which might help explain the significance of Rexroth’s experience to a philosophy of education: Rexroth’s educational formation transcended formal education by his deliberate pursuit of such non-formal strategies of learning as attending the at homes, hearing presentations from the soapbox, experimenting with artistic styles, movements, and forms, and later using radio broadcasting for the exploration of ideas. This list does not include his habitual use of educational opportunities presented by museums libraries, and other institutions, nor the intensive programs of reading he pursued, including an annual reading of the encyclopedia Britannica. Similar

incorporations of learning opportunities and strategies, if they are not reduced to devices of control through the suppression of expression and deliberate generation of falsities, can help liberate the individual from the strictures that often dominate formal educational systems. If they are not questioned, though, there is always an inherent danger in such openings, as the example of social media's creation of the Pizzagate scandal shows, not to mention the denial of the reality of very unfortunately real events, from election outcomes to claims that the Newtown shootings, not to mention the holocaust, never occurred. But informed incorporation of non-traditional educational strategies and opportunities such as those Rexroth pursued might provide a means for educational systems to overcome their too-common tendency to reduce individuals to a view that formal educational credentials are the be-all and end-all of education, all the while ignoring self-directed learning. Rexroth's accomplishments can in this way be seen as exemplary of self-directed autodidacticism, and could provide a model for the possibilities inherent in other forms of direct educational pursuit, even though such a pursuit may lead to the recognition that our understanding of the world is based on perspectives and is always only the temporary realization of truths as they are known at the present moment, and that they are always by necessity transient and ultimately set to be transcended.

Appendix

Sample of a Cubist painting by Kenneth Rexroth

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